

Predicting weight dispersion in seabass aquaculture using Discrete Event System simulation and Machine Learning modeling

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ABSTRACT

Marine aquaculture, particularly in the Mediterranean region, faces the challenge of minimizing growth dispersion, which has a direct impact on the production cycle, market value and sustainability of the sector. Conventional grading methods are resource intensive and potentially detrimental to fish health. The current study presented an innovative approach in predicting fish weight dispersion in European seabass (*Dicentrarchus labrax*) aquaculture. Seabass is one of the two major fish species cultivated on the Mediterranean coast, with a fattening cycle of 18–24 months. During this period, several grading operations are carried out to minimize growth dispersion. The intricate feed-fish-water system, characterized by complex interactions among feeding regimes, fish behavior, individual metabolism and environmental factors, is the focus of the study. The comprehensive, five-step methodology addresses this complexity. The process begins with a Discrete Event System (DES) model that simulates the feed-fish-water dynamics, taking into account individual fish metabolism. This is followed by the development of a surrogate machine learning (ML) regressor model, which is trained on DES simulation data to efficiently predict growth distribution. The model is then calibrated and customized for specific fish stocks and production tanks. The preliminary results from 21 tanks in two trials with European seabass (*D. labrax*) showed the effectiveness of the method. The results from the simulation models achieved a R^2 of 99.9 % and a Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) of 1.1 % for the prediction of mean final weight and a R^2 of 90.3 % with a MAPE of 8.1 % for the standard deviation of final weight. In summary, this study represents a significant advance in the planning and management of seabass aquaculture. Given the lack of effective prediction tools in the aquaculture industry, the proposed methodology has the potential to reduce risks and inefficiencies, thus possibly optimizing aquaculture practices by increasing sustainability and profitability.

1. Introduction

Aquaculture is the controlled process of cultivating aquatic

organisms, for commercial purposes. It is currently the world's fastest-growing food-production sector and is critical in meeting the increasing demand for seafood protein, [FAO \(2023\)](#). Despite providing

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an alternative seafood source, preventing overfishing and helping in rebuilding natural populations of depleted wild fish stocks, the aquaculture production cycle (Fig. 1) faces several challenges that can impact its growth and effective environmental sustainability.

One of the challenges faced by aquaculture farms is the maintenance of the homogeneity of fish weight in the rearing units throughout the production cycle, which is of paramount importance for several reasons, such as reducing aggression and cannibalism, improving feed efficiency and growth rates, ensuring predictable harvests, and supporting sustainability goals. Thus, striving for homogeneity of fish weight in the individual units is therefore essential to maximizing production efficiency, maintaining fish welfare and promoting responsible and profitable aquaculture practices.

To minimize weight heterogeneity in the production units, aquaculture farms perform grading procedures which consist of the sorting of fish based on size or weight. These procedures play an important role in shaping various aspects of the aquaculture production cycle and can have direct and indirect effects on the overall production outcome since this practice is costly, labor intensive and animal handling can increase the risk of disease and mortality. In addition, the ability of the farmers to predict fish weight distribution during the growth cycle is a critical success factor in optimizing the grading process and stock management and allows fish farmers to pre-negotiate the sale of a fish based on weight classes.

Aquaculture farm management may highly benefit from supportive automated tools such as numerical modeling, which can simulate and predict various scenarios in aquaculture facilities, leading to optimization and automation of system management, higher profitability and environmental sustainability (Bricker et al., 2016; Joffre et al., 2015; Nobre et al., 2009). These models have been developed and applied for a broad range of aquaculture systems, such as Recirculating Aquaculture System (RAS) Hathurusingha and Davey (2014), coastal and offshore systems Ferreira et al. (2009) and various fish species, such as Tilapia (*O. niloticus*) Lin and Chen (2021), Gilthead seabream (*S. aurata*) Žužul et al. (2019) and others.

Most numerical models are continuous-time (take into account the continuous changes of the system over time) and are generally based on a set of ordinary differential equations that define the rates of change of the state variables.

These models are able to address a wide range of features, such as: hydrodynamic models that predict physical properties and the water currents (Chen and Christensen, 2017; Cheng et al., 2020; Correia et al., 2019; Henderson et al., 2001; Herrera et al., 2018; Urke et al., 2021; Wu et al., 2014); water quality/bio-geo-chemistry models for water quality and nutrient dynamics (Ferreira et al., 2007, 2009; Islam, 2005; Stigebrandt et al., 2004; Wild-Allen et al., 2010); population dynamics models for fish growth, survival and interactions between fish species (Lin and Chen, 2021; Murray and Munro, 2018; Žužul et al., 2019); and

biological and energetic models to predict energy requirements for growth, reproduction and maintenance (Axler et al., 1993; Cacho, 1990; Cho and Bureau, 1998; Cuenco et al., 1985).

In addition, several growth models have been developed based on the simulation of the metabolism of individual fish. Chary et al. (2022) provides a comprehensive and organized review of fish farm-scale models published during the period from 1985 to 2021. Nevertheless, weight dispersion is rarely considered as a predictive outcome and no specific data are available on this metric.

In the context of Industry 4.0, there are intensive research activities on bringing digital technologies, automation, data exchange, cloud computing, artificial intelligence into the aquaculture production cycle Fig. 1, i.e. Precision Fish Farming (PFF) or Aquaculture 4.0 (Føre et al., 2018; Wang et al., 2021). PFF aims to optimize, modernize and automate fish farming operations. A notable benefit for aquaculture is the integration of computer vision for non-invasive sampling, measuring, and monitoring of fish health and behavior. Utilizing computer vision, traditional machine learning algorithms, and deep learning techniques embedded in monitoring, control, and management systems can enhance rearing conditions and operational outcomes. These features are crucial in developing new and improved farming methods, including real-time monitoring, early problem detection optimization, cost reduction, data-driven decision-making, improvement of fish welfare, and enabling a holistic understanding of aquaculture facilities.

Yang et al. (2020) discussed several studies on the incorporation of these principles and developed new tools for non-manipulative methods, for applications such as: species identification Li et al. (2016); fish counting and size measurement Voskakis et al. (2021); biomass estimation Abinaya et al. (2022); disease detection Nayan et al. (2021); behavioral anomalies related to stress and disease (Zhao et al. (2021), Yang et al. (2021b), Kandimalla et al. (2022)); behavioral analysis and growth monitoring Cisar et al. (2021); and feeding behavior analysis (Wei et al. (2022), Yang et al. (2021a), Li et al. (2020)), which can enable accurate feeding according to fish requirements and minimize feed wastage.

Machine learning (ML) involves the development of algorithms that enable computers to learn patterns from data and make predictions or decisions without being explicitly programmed (Bishop, 2006; Murphy, 2012; Theodoridis, 2020). In aquaculture, ML is regarded as a key technology for feeding control (Zhou et al., 2017, 2019) and water quality management (Najah Ahmed et al., 2019; Chen et al., 2020).

Another technology that can be useful in aquaculture is Discrete Event System (DES) simulation, which is a modeling and analysis technique that can be used to simulate the behavior of complex systems over time, Cassandras and Lafortune (2021). In this approach, a system is represented as a series of discrete events that occur chronologically. Each event triggers changes in the state of the system, and the simulation tracks these state changes to analyze the performance, behavior, and

Fig. 1. Aquaculture production cycle.

optimization of the system.

DES is widely used in manufacturing, logistics, healthcare, and transportation to study and improve these processes. In aquaculture, DES models have been applied successfully either individually [Slette et al. \(2022\)](#) or in combination with continuous-time stochastic simulations to track production status, establish early warning systems [Guarini et al. \(2021\)](#), gain a deeper understanding of financial decisions in the supply chain [Oleghe \(2020\)](#) and to consider potential operational and environmental constraints to maximize annual profits [Halachmi et al. \(2014\)](#).

DES offers a simplified but effective approach compared to continuous-time models. This study utilizes DES to model fish metabolism through events spanning from feed distribution to excretion, providing a comprehensive integration of system relationships that simulate the interaction between feeding, fish stock, and water parameters.

European seabass (*Dicentrarchus labrax*) is one of most cultivated species in Europe. Seabass has a fattening cycle of 18–24 months, from fry (1.5–2.5 g) to sale weight (0.4–0.5 kg), depending on feed nutrients and the water conditions such as: temperature, salinity and dissolved oxygen ([FAO, 2009](#); [FAO-AFFRIS, 2024](#)).

During the production cycle, a minimum of three grading operations are carried out to minimize growth dispersion. They are mainly reared in natural environments, such as coastal cages, estuarine ponds and recirculating aquaculture systems (RAS), where water parameters and feeding are better controlled. Homogeneity in harvesting is desirable, as the most common harvest size should be between 0.4 and 0.5 kg, which is the fish size required by restaurants and supermarkets. Based on data provided in [Di Trapani et al. \(2014\)](#) which compare production costs and revenues from in-shore and off-shore aquaculture of European seabass (*D. labrax*), the total cost of production is approximately divided into 38 % of feeding, 31 % fingerlings, 15 % labor and 16 % of other expenses (repair and maintenance, packaging, fuels, and other).

This study aimed to develop a novel, robust and multidisciplinary methodology to overcome the challenges of predicting growth and weight distribution of European seabass (*D. labrax*) in aquaculture systems. To do that, interdisciplinary knowledge from aquaculture research, fish biology, control engineering, computer science and software engineering are required. The gain of the proposed methodology is roughly estimated at about an increase of 6 % of the final economic result. Of this, 2 % comes from the 10 % reduction in feeding due to optimized feeding using optimization models and what-if scenarios, 1 % from the cost of grading procedures, optimization of time and distribution, and the other 3 % from the revenue increase 5 % due to the pre-negotiated prices per size at harvest achieved by the new predictive capabilities and management practices used by the method.

This paper is organized as follows: [Section 1](#) provides a general summary of the scope of the paper and the technologies applied to aquaculture production in the context of the problem addressed. [Section 2](#) explains and conceptually describes the proposed methodology for developing a predictive model for a given fish stock in a production unit. [Section 3](#) describes the experimental setup and software implementation for evaluating the first three steps of the proposed methodology. [Section 4](#) presents the results of the experimental assessment of the methodology. [Section 5](#) discusses the successes and limitations of the experimental testing and suggests future research and development to improve the results and validate the end-to-end methodology. And finally, in [section 6](#), the conclusions of this work are presented.

2. Proposed methodology for weight dispersion prediction

Accurately predicting the weight distribution of fish stock during the growth production cycle is a significant challenge, as data acquisition from live fish trials are resource intensive. However, numerous studies on fish metabolism and growth models, especially for European seabass (*D. Labrax*), provide a basis for such predictive models.

The physiological diversity within fish populations and behavioral aspects such as dominance increase the complexity of modeling the results. In addition, each fish population may have additional variability within its assigned production unit, such as tanks or ponds, which requires adaptation of the model.

2.1. Feed-fish-water system simulation using DES modelling

The proposed method integrates the feeding behavior of individual fish and metabolic models into a stochastic system simulation that models growth based on probabilistic behavioral parameters. The results of fish stock growth are aggregated daily by processing the ingested feed units. The top-level abstraction representing the model of the feed-fish-water system is shown in [Figs. 2](#) and [3](#) illustrates the implementation architecture of the DES system. The impact on the environment is also assessed through the interaction of feeding and metabolism with the water system.

In aquaculture production units, there are system components with different properties:

- The **metabolism of fish** and the **dynamics of chemicals in water** are continuous-time systems because they involve physical and chemical reactions. For more accurate modeling, differential equations would be used. But in this particular case, each fish contributes with a small part of the effect, and the timing can be divided into discrete time segments with a resolution that does not affect the accuracy of the system simulation;
- **Feed dispensing** is a discrete-time component because the pellets are discrete units that are output, and feed throughput is an average of the weight of pellets output per unit of time;
- **Feed intake** is a stochastic, event-based system because it depends on the position of the fish in the tank and its ability to compete with other fish in the production unit.

Given these properties, fish, feeding, and feed intake can be modeled in a hybrid system described and simulated by a DES model. Fish is a continuous-time process (digestion and water) that can be modeled by a periodic sequence of discrete-time events (where periodicity is determined by a resolution that approximates continuous time in the system dynamics). Feeding can be modeled by a periodic sequence of discrete events in pellet delivery, and feed intake is inherently a process based on discrete events.

In this study, the growth of the total biomass of the fish stock was determined by aggregating data from each individual fish, as simulated by the aforementioned DES model. This simulation includes numerous events resulting from the digestion of pellet portions ingested by each fish. Consequently, simulating a single day involves a large number of events, making it time-consuming and resource-intensive. Despite their high computational cost, DES simulations are significantly more cost-effective and resource-efficient than real animal trials once the DES model has been calibrated.

2.2. Machine Learning surrogate model development

A machine learning surrogate model, termed the Species Model, was developed to efficiently replicate the aggregated results of the simulator. The ML model requires far fewer computing resources and reacts faster than DES, so applications such as control systems for feeding are possible near in real time.

An outstanding feature of the data-driven approach is its adaptability and evolution. Trained machine learning models can evolve through regular updates and retraining is critical to maintaining their effectiveness and relevance. This process allows models to capture changes in data distributions, improve performance and overcome challenges such as concept drift.

The Random Forest (RF) regressor was chosen for its efficiency and

Fig. 2. Top-level of abstraction of feed-fish-water system implementation.

Fig. 3. System implementation architecture.

simplicity. RF is a non-parametric regression model developed by (Breiman, 2001, 1996) and is an effective ensemble algorithm that uses multiple decision trees to compute the regression result. The aggregated result of the multiple regression trees increases accuracy and robustness. This is the ML algorithm used in the proposed method to predict the aggregate outcomes of the simulations based on their input settings.

Hyperparameterization is usually a way to more effectively adapt ML algorithms to the target phenomenon. Instead of algorithm hyperparameters, in this framework we define model hyperparameters as a set of input variables that can be used to fit the generalized fish species ML model to a specific model for a production unit (specific fish stock and tank or pond). In this work, the adaptation of the hyperparameterization for a specific production tank is done by optimizing the prediction results based on early-stage measurements of a tank fish stock.

To customize the generic Species Model for specific tanks or ponds, hyperparameters must be optimized with regard to fish stock and tank characteristics. The result is a tank-specific model that is active until the fish grading occurs.

2.3. Summary of the end-to-end methodology

The methodology is illustrated visually in the Appendix. It is divided into two phases and five steps. Steps 1–3 belong to the development phase of the models and steps 4–5 belong to the production phase:

1. Construct a DES model from the literature on growth and metabolism of fish species. Run several scenarios to generate a dataset (Appendix, Fig. 11).
2. Train and validate the ML species model for predicting weight dispersion using the dataset generated by the DES simulation. (Appendix, Fig. 12).
3. Validate the ML species model with experimental data, optimize the hyperparameters and test the tank-specific model (Appendix, Fig. 13).
4. Optimize the hyperparameter and validate a specific tank model in the initial production phase (Appendix, Fig. 13).

5. Deploy the customized model in production. Update the hyperparameters for the target tanks after the fish have been classified or relocated (Appendix, Fig. 14).

The goal of step 1 is to create a simulation model that can synthetically generate data about the fish growth and weight dispersion for the training of a machine learning model in multiple scenarios of variations on the input simulation. Nutritional trials and growth models (energy based) of European seabass (*D. labrax*) articles in the literature provide the basis for the DES simulation processes definition. The scenarios should cover the range of temperature, salinity, dissolved oxygen, and other input parameters according the variations on the natural habitat and also the observed rearing conditions in aquaculture of European seabass (*D. labrax*) species.

Step 2 aims to develop a model for the European seabass (*D. labrax*), that can run with the required response time and smaller computational footprint than the simulator, to be utilized in a planning software or the control system, replicating the results of the DES simulator when used with the same input data. Machine learning regression model is used because its performance at production, i. e., the model utilization for predictions.

Step 3 is the validation and testing of the species model (in this case the European seabass surrogate ML model) and its hyperparametrization to ensure it can be deployed for production use. It consists of testing the model against measured data from laboratory trials and aquaculture production units and evaluating the precision of the predictions after the hyperparametrization optimization of the model for specific fish stocks and tanks. As the model is approved on the validation and tests, it is available to deploy into European seabass aquaculture production.

The software is ready for use after step 3, then steps 4 and 5 are the procedures for the customization of the model for a specific aquaculture production unit, and the consequent adjustments necessary when fish is transferred between tanks in the grading and biomass density adequation processes. Every production unit with its fish stock is an unique model that should be adjusted at the early stages using the measured fish and rearing conditions on the specific tank. Computer vision devices and data acquisition from sensors can effectively collect data for the specific model customization.

3. Materials and methods

Initial evaluations of the proposed methodology were conducted, comprising steps 1–3 described in Section 2.3, for the European seabass (*D. labrax*) species using data collected in two *in vivo* trials at CHIMAR-UP (2024), Portugal. The implementation of these three steps is detailed in the following subsections.

3.1. Metrics for fish growth assessment

The metrics used to evaluate the growth of a fish stock during a period of time are defined by the following equations, that aggregates the initial weight of individual fish comparing to their final aggregated weight and variation:

$$\bar{w}_0 = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{n_0} w_{0,i}}{n_0} \quad (1)$$

$$\bar{w}_f = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^{n_f} w_{f,j}}{n_f} \quad (2)$$

$$\bar{g} = \bar{w}_0 - \bar{w}_f \quad (3)$$

$$\bar{r}\bar{g} = \frac{\bar{g}}{\bar{w}_0} \quad (4)$$

$$\sigma(w_f) = \frac{\sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^{n_f} (w_{f,j} - \bar{w}_f)^2}}{n_f} \quad (5)$$

$$CV(w_f) = \frac{\sigma(w_f)}{\bar{w}_f} \quad (6)$$

where $w_{0,i}$ and $w_{f,j}$ is initial and final weight of individual fish, n_0 and n_f are the number of fish in the initial and final stock, \bar{g} is the mean growth, $\bar{r}\bar{g}$ is the relative mean growth, $\sigma(w_f)$ is the standard deviation of the final weight and $CV(w_f)$ is the coefficient of variation (CV) of the final weight.

The DES simulation provides the data of the individual fish, which makes it possible to calculate growth on an individual level. However, for practical purposes, growth should be expressed using metrics that are normalized for the fish stock, and can be compared between different trials and production units. Growth is then expressed as relative mean growth, i.e. the growth relative to the initial weight, and as the coefficient of variation of the final weight, i.e. the standard deviation relative to the mean final weight.

3.2. DES simulation implementation and execution

The implementation of the Discrete Event System (DES) simulation focuses on a reduced model of fish feeding and digestion in an aquaculture tank. Key dynamics such as fish dominance, satiety, and metabolic efficiency are modeled, which affect total biomass, growth dispersion and water parameters.

The modular structure of the simulation provides a robust and configurable DES kernel that supports future extensions and improvements to the subsystem model without changing the kernel. This includes automata, relationships and equations.

The system simulates a European seabass (*D. labrax*) tank without water exchange, focusing on the effects of feeding and digestion on water quality parameters such as dissolved oxygen, total ammonium nitrogen (TAN) and dissolved organic matter (DOM).

The input parameters determine the process to be simulated for each day in a row, i.e., the state variables of the simulator are kept between each day. The total number of fish and their combined weight establish the population and biomass within the tank. Variability in initial weights of the fish is captured by the initial weight dispersion, expressed as the standard deviation. Daily feed mass is adjusted as a percentage of the total required for a single feeding satiation, calculated based on the fish's average weight and environmental factors, with values like 0.8 (for underfeeding) to 2.2 (for overfeeding), and provided in one or two dispensing periods with duration and interval between them. Environmental conditions are simplified into sinusoidal variations for average daily temperature and salinity, tailored to either mimic realistic weather patterns or maintain consistency in controlled environments. Additionally, the dominance score standard deviation models the variance in fish competitiveness, affecting their access to food and subsequent growth.

Configuration parameters for each of the three main components: feeder, fish stock, and water environment, adjust the equations and model processes setting up the model that replicates the biological process. Those parameters are: pellets weight, coefficients of the equations that models the fish appetite as a function of the satiation level and the winner in a pellet dispute based on that level and the individual dominance index, the general Feed Conversion Rate (FCR) and its variance used to determine the fish growth in the digestion of each digestion portion of a pellet, the excretion amount of matter, accumulation and time to expel the digested feed, among others.

The feeder initiates interactions with its feeding schedule and influences feed wastage and growth dispersion. The configuration of the feeding schedule affects fish growth and pellet waste.

The appetite, dominance and position of each fish determine the probability that it will eat an issued pellet. The Fish Stock component is

complex as each fish independently ingests food, digests and defecates. The growth is computed based on the configured general FCR applied to each ingested pellet. Consumed oxygen, produced carbon dioxide and ammonia are also computed at the digestion of each pellet. These processes affect the water quality and body mass of the fish but are simplified without reducing the overall accuracy of the model.

The water environment model reflects the effects of fish digestion and focuses on the temporal evolution of oxygen demand, carbon dioxide, TAN and fecal excretion. However, they are not used in this work as the focus of the models is on validating the estimation of weight dispersion, and experiments were conducted in RAS laboratory tanks with water flow, aeration and biofilters to ensure good rearing conditions.

The results are recorded in the output file for every simulated day. A reporting component logs the evolution of the output variables and the internal state and creates charts at the end of each simulated day like the examples in Figs. 4 and 5. The daily output includes the initial and final biomass in kg, the initial and final number of fish (if mortality is configured, the number of fish may decrease during the simulation days), the fish mean and standard deviation of the initial and final stock in g, the total amount of food given and ingested in kg, the total variation of dissolved oxygen ($\frac{mg}{T}$), and carbon dioxide ($\frac{mg}{T}$), TAN ($\frac{mg}{T}$) and feces ($\frac{mg}{T}$) into the tank. From those metrics only growth-related ones (initial and final mean weight and standard deviations, and initial and final number of fish) are further used to train and validate the surrogate ML model, as at this point the results of interest are related only to growth dispersion. In the future ML models will cover other than the weight dispersion predictors.

The supplementary material contains a detailed description of the DES simulation system, inputs, configurations, subsystems and associated automata, state variables and events, and outputs Fig. 6.

3.3. Surrogate ML model implementation and execution

For the surrogate ML model, not all the detailed output of the simulation is considered, the model focused on two predictors: Relative Growth Mean and Final Weight CV. These were derived from the aggregated daily results of the feeding and water parameter simulations (Eqs. (4) and (6)). These predictors were selected for their analytical importance to evaluate growth metrics and weight dispersion and to show the relationship between initial and final weight in stock.

For each of those two predictors, a RF regressor was developed using the scikit-learn Python library [sklearn \(2022\)](#). Each regressor was evaluated for its performance and ability to avoid overfitting. The dataset was divided into 10 partitions. For the performance evaluation, 10 rounds of training and validation were performed. In each round, 7 partitions were randomly selected for training and the remaining 3 partitions for testing. The global criterion ensured that each partition participated in 3 rounds as a validation set, with all validation datasets being mutually exclusive, i.e. no combination of the 3 partitions was repeated. Using this methodology, different combinations of 7 partitions were ensured for the training datasets. In this way, the average prediction performance and the standard deviation were calculated, which provide information about the generalization ability of the model with different inputs.

The ML model is trained and validated to obtain the same results of the DES simulation each day, based on the input and outputs dataset generated by the simulator under multiple scenarios.

3.4. European seabass (*D. labrax*) model validation

To validate the ML surrogate model for the European seabass species, which consequently validates the DES model, data from weight measurements of European seabass (*D. labrax*) in two *in vivo* trials of the ACCESS2SEA project [Access2Sea \(2022\)](#) conducted at CIIMAR-UP facilities [CIIMAR-UP \(2024\)](#), Portugal, were utilized. The Bioterium of

Fig. 4. Example of fish metrics in a daily simulation.

Simulation of system FishTank - Growth

Fig. 5. Example of growth results in a daily simulation.

Fig. 6. Sequence of events relate to a pellet intake and digestion.

Aquatic Organisms (BOGA) at CIIMAR-UP operates within the framework of Legislative Decree No. 113/2013 and adheres to the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity (<https://www2.ciimar.up.pt/documents/Code-of-Conduct-for-Research-Integrity.png>).

In the first trial, which lasted 6 weeks, 288 fish (average initial body weight: 23 g) were distributed over 12 tanks. The temperature was set at

17, 21, 26°C. Salinity was altered weekly and was set 15, 38, 21, 33, 27, 45 ppt in each respective week of the trial, with the control group maintained at 21°C and 38 ppt. The second trial, which also lasted 6 weeks, involved 198 fish (average initial body weight: 86 g) in 9 tanks at temperatures of 21, 26 and 17°C. The salinity followed the same pattern as in the first trial. Both trials used 200-liter tanks connected to a

Recirculating Aquaculture System (RAS) to ensure stable conditions and the fish were fed to satiation.

The fish were weighed at the beginning and end of each trial without identifying them individually. This approach only allows an aggregated growth analysis. Daily feeding, temperature and salinity data were used as input parameters to the model to predict subsequent days' weight over a 42-day period.

The input features of the regression model that were considered as hyperparameters for specific experimental tanks included:

- **FCR** - Digestion-to-metabolism feed conversion parameter.
- **dominance std** - Parameter for fish dominance in feeding.
- **efficiency** - Mean metabolic efficiency factor for tank simulations.

The hyperparameters were optimized using a grid search algorithm, since the random forest regressor models cannot be derived. The loss function summed the squared errors between the observed and predicted mean and standard deviation of the final weight.

3.5. Metrics for predictive performance evaluation of the models

The metrics defined in Table 1 are used in this paper to evaluate the prediction performance of the models, comparing the expected value (value that should be produced to zero error) and the predicted value (output of the model).

Although R^2 is often used to evaluate the performance of regression models, it measures how the model outcome is explained by the model's input variables, which sometimes does not provide a complete understanding of predictive accuracy. The error metrics give more information about how accurate the prediction is, and the MAPE in particular is more intuitive to understand the accuracy of the prediction results.

4. Results

The metrics defined in Table 1 are used to evaluate the regression models and validate the prediction of the specific tank models against the real measurements at the end of the live fish trials.

4.1. DES simulation results

The discrete event simulation (DES) generates results for training the surrogate machine learning (ML) model. A combination of grid and random search strategies was used for 12 scenarios. Each scenario consists of nine dataset parameters: a) food conversion ratio (FCR), b) feeding flow rate, c) feeding interval in hours, d) feeding per weight percentage, e) standard deviation of dominance index, f) initial weight

Table 1

Perform metrics for evaluation predictions of continuous variables. w_j is the expected value of a measurement of a variable, and \widehat{w}_j is the predicted value of the variable.

Metric	Formula
R2-Score (R^2)	$1 - \frac{\sum_{j=1}^N (\widehat{w}_j - w_j)^2}{\sum_{j=1}^N (\overline{w} - w_j)^2}$
Mean Squared Error (MSE)	$\frac{1}{N} \sum_{j=1}^N (\widehat{w}_j - w_j)^2$
Mean Absolute Error (MAE)	$\frac{1}{N} \sum_{j=1}^N \widehat{w}_j - w_j $
Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE)	$\frac{1}{N} \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^N (\widehat{w}_j - w_j)^2}$
Root Mean Squared Percentage Error (RMSPE)	$\frac{100}{N} \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^N \left(\frac{\widehat{w}_j - w_j}{w_j}\right)^2}$
Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE)	$\frac{100}{N} \sum_{j=1}^N \left(\frac{ \widehat{w}_j - w_j }{w_j}\right)$
Symmetric Mean Absolute Percentage Error (SMAPE)	$\frac{100}{N} \sum_{j=1}^N \left(\frac{ \widehat{w}_j - w_j }{(\widehat{w}_j + w_j)/2}\right)$

mean, g) coefficient of variation (CV) of initial weight, h) temperature, and i) salinity. Lists of values for each input parameter were generated for each scenario, including a set of randomly selected values for each parameter. The grid and random search algorithm selects combinations of the nine input parameters, using scenarios for the minimum, average, and maximum values, as well as random combinations within the configured input range. Dataset parameters are then generated daily, considering the initial value chosen for each scenario and the daily evolution in the simulation over multiple days.

Simulations were conducted over specific time periods, with all parameters held constant except one, which varied over the entire range of values. Although this method does not examine every possible combination of parameters, it ensures that all values of a single parameter are tested in conjunction with randomly selected values of other parameters. This approach simplifies the analysis of the influence of individual parameters on the simulation results and aids in performing sensitivity analyses.

Table 2 shows the input parameters covered by the executed scenarios. Although the DES simulation results provide more outputs than the relative growth mean and final weight CV, other results are discarded because the focus of the model in this paper is to generate data to evaluate growth in multiple scenarios, training the ML model, and validating the growth results using the data from the trials in the laboratory tanks. Since it is difficult to present the results of the 11029 daily simulations generated by the 12 scenarios with combined random variations of the 7 input parameters in a summarizing table, these results are presented for the relative growth mean in Fig. 7 and for the final weight CV in Fig. 8.

4.2. Machine learning model results

Each dataset represents the simulation of one day. Of note, the Final Weight CV tends to align with the CV due to minimal daily variation, but over successive weeks (as in the trials in subsection 3.4) the cumulative effects become significant.

The dataset, comprising 11029 daily recordings, was divided into 10 partitions for training and validation of two regressors: one for Relative Growth Mean and the other for Final Weight CV. Each partition, consisting of approximately 1103 records, was used in 10 rounds, with a 70:30 split for training and validation. This ensured that each partition underwent 3 rounds of validation. The prediction performance metrics for these rounds are summarized in Table 3.

Fig. 9 compares the output daily simulation values with the values predicted by the random forest regressor models for Relative Growth Mean and Final Weight CV.

4.3. Specific tank models validation results

For the validation of the ML model optimized with hyperparameters specific to each tank the observed data of all 21 tanks, 12 in the first trial and 9 in the second trial, are compared with the results of the corresponding model prediction. Using the model output: Relative Growth mean and Final Weight CV, the final predicted weight mean and standard deviation are calculated.

Table 4 contains the data from 21 tanks where fish were kept in two trials, highlighting the weight variation at the corresponding temperature during the trial and the weekly variation in salinity. Also shown in the table are the optimized hyperparameter values for digestion FCR, the standard deviation of the dominance index and the mean efficiency factor, as well as the predicted mean and standard deviation of the final weight to facilitate comparison with the observed experimental results. Fig. 10 provides a visual representation of these comparisons.

Table 5 provides a summary of the model's predictive performance for European seabass (*D. labrax*), comparing the observed and predicted final weight mean and standard deviation for each tank.

Homoscedasticity refers to the homogeneity of variance, implying

Table 2
Number of simulation periods with parameters changes.

changed aramerter	number of periods	total days	days per period			parameter range		
			mean	min	max	min	max	values
p								
FCR	140	700	5.0	5	5	1.00	1.85	18
feeding flow rate	276	1556	5.6	4	10	0.2	1.0	20
feeding interval	308	1716	5.6	4	10	0.0	4.4	28
feeding per weight	280	1576	5.6	4	10	0.4 %	26 %	20
dominance std	276	1556	5.6	4	10	2.0 %	20 %	25
initial weight mean	280	1576	5.6	4	10	25	250	10
initial weight CV	280	1576	5.6	4	10	2.5 %	20 %	23
temperature	210	1182	5.6	4	10	19	28	16
salinity	207	1167	5.6	4	10	18	30	18
Total	1977	11029						

that the variance of the errors is assumed to be constant across all levels of the independent variables. To validate the use of R^2 -score as performance metric, the homoscedasticity of the residuals (prediction errors for each sample) was tested using the Breusch-Pagan Lagrange Multiplier test for heteroscedasticity (Breusch and Pagan, 1979; statsmodels.org, 2024) for the regression model results shown in Table 3 and the models hyperparameterization optimization presented in Table 4, which are illustrated in Figs. 9 and 10 respectively.

Three out of four model outputs (two of ML model regressors and two of optimized hyperparameters models) did not satisfy homoscedasticity when comparing the prediction error with the real measured values, indicating that the R^2 -score alone is not fully representative of the model's quality. Therefore, additional metrics such as MAPE and SMAPE are used to better represent prediction error and assess the quality of the trained ML regression models in this study. MAPE and SMAPE can be adversely affected by zeros and large outliers; however, these are not present in the dataset.

4.4. Computing environment and repository

For the test simulations, the DES system used an ASUS TUF notebook equipped with an AMD Ryzen 7 3750 H processor, a Radeon Vega Mobile Gfx 2.30 GHz, 8 GB RAM, an NVIDIA GeForce GTX 1660 Ti, a 64-bit Windows 10 Home and Python 3.11.0.

It took about 60 h to simulate 11029 days from the dataset, an average of 20 s per day. The longest simulation took approximately 1 min and 55 s, with time variations mainly due to the number of pellets issued affecting the total number of events in the DES simulation. The longest simulation processed approximately 1.6×10^6 events.

The training and validation of the two ML models for growth mean and final weight CV over 10 rounds and the final model training took a total of 166 s

Fitting the hyperparameters for the two ML models for 21 tanks took 4 h, 32 min and 28 s, with 363,300 optimization rounds processed over 42 days. The prediction for one day thus took about 1.07 ms, regardless of the daily input parameters.

The developed code, simulation results and logs are stored in a repository, which is available on request.

5. Discussion and future work

The discussion addresses three main topics: the predictive performance analysis of the models based on the results presented in Section 4, the comparison and implications of time and resource consumption between DES simulations and surrogate ML models, and improvements in the implementation of the end-to-end methodology to enable its use in production systems for monitoring, controlling, and optimizing feeding according rearing conditions, as well as planning production outcomes.

5.1. Evaluation of predictive performance in DES and ML models

Intraday data on water quality, feeding and growth of individual fish are essential for the calibration and evaluation of DES simulation results. As these data are currently not available, they will be collected in future trials. The evaluation of the DES simulation was qualitative and focused on analyzing the daily simulation trends in graphs.

The metrics on the predictive performance of the random forest regressors (Table 3) in 10 rounds of validation show high efficiency in replicating the overall results of the daily simulations, with the low standard deviation indicating the stability of the model and the generalization of the input data. Fig. 9 shows a small error in the predicted simulation results by the ML model under the same input conditions.

The metrics in Table 5 and the comparisons between observed and predicted results (Fig. 10) of the hyperparameter optimized model for each of the 21 tanks, demonstrate good prediction performance for the weight mean with reasonable standard deviation performance considering the simplified, uncalibrated DES simulation.

Despite the lower error in the final weight mean, the tanks show a higher error at 17°C (groups 1 and 5), indicating the need for further research into the temperature sensitivity of the growth model.

The higher standard deviation error in the tanks of the second trial indicates that the model for growth variation was adjusted to the higher initial weight. The variation, which is mainly due to differences in feed intake, requires a review of feed intake and feeding competition in relation to initial weight.

The most common accuracy metrics for ML regression models are prediction errors such as MSE, RMSE, RMSPE, MAE, MAPE, and SMAPE as defined in Table 1. Additionally, the R^2 -score is frequently used to assess prediction performance in ML regression models. While the R^2 provides useful information, it has limitations that may make it less suitable in certain contexts, particularly in non-linear regression models (Spiess and Neumeier, 2010; Plevris et al., 2022). As shown in Table 6 the R^2 -score could not representative alone for models evaluation, it is provided as the prediction errors are small confirming the R^2 -score good results.

5.2. Comparison of time and resource usage: DES Simulation vs. Surrogate ML Model

The feed-fish-water simulation provides more detailed results regarding changes in water quality parameters compared to the ML model. However, for similar control applications, the ML model is 20,000 times faster and suitable for real-time use, highlighting the significant advantage of converting simulation models to an ML model approach, which offers far superior scalability.

The time and resource consumption of DES simulations are proportional to the number of events processed. Dispensed pellets trigger initial events for intake, digestion, and excretion processes, with the duration of these processes depending on the granularity and complexity of their internal computations. Consequently, consumption is heavily dependent

Fig. 7. Dataset (simulation output) visualization of the predictor relative growth mean as function of the input features.

Fig. 8. Dataset (simulation output) visualization of the predictor final weight CV as function of the input features.

Table 3
Performance metrics of Random forest regressors for 10 rounds validation on replicating simulation daily results.

round	num. vectors	R2	MSE	RMSE	RMSPE	MAE	MAPE	SMAPE
Regressor for Final Weight CV								
1	3343	0.9998	6.02E-07	7.76E-04	0.91 %	3.89E-04	0.44 %	0.44 %
2	3322	0.9998	5.48E-07	7.40E-04	0.81 %	3.70E-04	0.40 %	0.40 %
3	3349	0.9998	5.63E-07	7.50E-04	0.87 %	3.77E-04	0.41 %	0.42 %
4	3313	0.9998	5.12E-07	7.15E-04	0.83 %	3.66E-04	0.40 %	0.40 %
5	3307	0.9998	5.54E-07	7.44E-04	0.87 %	3.78E-04	0.42 %	0.42 %
6	3272	0.9998	5.71E-07	7.55E-04	0.87 %	3.74E-04	0.42 %	0.42 %
7	3287	0.9998	5.68E-07	7.53E-04	0.89 %	3.75E-04	0.42 %	0.42 %
8	3305	0.9998	6.10E-07	7.81E-04	0.94 %	3.80E-04	0.43 %	0.43 %
9	3316	0.9998	5.65E-07	7.52E-04	0.91 %	3.76E-04	0.43 %	0.43 %
10	3273	0.9998	5.51E-07	7.42E-04	0.89 %	3.77E-04	0.42 %	0.42 %
min	3272	0.9998	5.12E-07	7.15E-04	0.81 %	3.66E-04	0.40 %	0.40 %
mean	3309	0.9998	5.64E-07	7.51E-04	0.88 %	3.76E-04	0.42 %	0.42 %
std	25	0.0000	2.63E-08	1.75E-05	0.04 %	5.72E-06	0.01 %	0.01 %
max	3349	0.9998	6.10E-07	7.81E-04	0.94 %	3.89E-04	0.44 %	0.44 %
Regressor for Relative Growth mean								
1	3343	0.9967	8.33E-07	9.12E-04	2.59 %	3.15E-04	1.05 %	1.05 %
2	3322	0.9972	7.19E-07	8.48E-04	2.34 %	3.02E-04	1.00 %	1.00 %
3	3349	0.9964	9.35E-07	9.67E-04	2.48 %	3.27E-04	1.07 %	1.06 %
4	3313	0.9962	9.68E-07	9.84E-04	2.79 %	3.42E-04	1.13 %	1.11 %
5	3307	0.9956	1.07E-06	1.03E-03	3.16 %	3.48E-04	1.17 %	1.15 %
6	3272	0.9958	1.01E-06	1.01E-03	3.16 %	3.54E-04	1.23 %	1.22 %
7	3287	0.9953	1.19E-06	1.09E-03	3.13 %	3.59E-04	1.20 %	1.19 %
8	3305	0.9961	9.91E-07	9.95E-04	2.75 %	3.35E-04	1.13 %	1.13 %
9	3316	0.9962	9.73E-07	9.87E-04	2.78 %	3.37E-04	1.14 %	1.14 %
10	3273	0.9968	7.97E-07	8.93E-04	2.57 %	3.21E-04	1.07 %	1.07 %
min	3272	0.9953	7.19E-07	8.48E-04	2.34 %	3.02E-04	1.00 %	1.00 %
mean	3309	0.9962	9.48E-07	9.72E-04	2.77 %	3.34E-04	1.12 %	1.11 %
std	25	0.0005	1.30E-07	6.71E-05	0.28 %	1.70E-05	0.07 %	0.06 %
max	3349	0.9972	1.19E-06	1.09E-03	3.16 %	3.59E-04	1.23 %	1.22 %

Fig. 9. Comparison of daily aggregated simulation output versus machine learning model predicted values for: (Left) relative growth mean, (Right) final weight CV. The closer to the diagonal line, the better the results.

on the daily amount of feed and, therefore, the size of the fish stock under simulation. This makes simulating large aquaculture production units much more resource-intensive.

In contrast, the time and resource consumption of the surrogate ML model are not dependent on the number of pellets dispensed or the complexity of the intake, digestion, and excretion processes. This is because the ML model is trained with a normalized summary of daily simulation results. As a result, the consumption remains nearly constant for predicting each day. This is a crucial feature of the methodology, as simulations can be conducted on a smaller scale while the production model is optimized, with the normalized parameters maintained within the trained model's range.

The speed of the execution of the surrogate ML model allows extensive number of optimization rounds, which could be required for the hyper-parameterization optimization necessary for the

customization of the species model for specific fish populations and production units. This adaptability for the uniqueness of each production unit is a requirement and an advantage of the proposed method.

5.3. Future methodological improvements

Chary et al. (2022) presented a review of 36 farm models (1985–2021), focusing on biomass and average weight, but not weight dispersion. Føre et al. (2016) provides a qualitative model analysis for Atlantic salmon (*S. salar*) and discusses factors influencing weight dispersion such as gut capacity and movement speed. Serpa et al. (2013) compares two DEB models for White seabream (*D. sargus*) and Gilthead seabream (*S. aurata*) and shows how DEB parameters influence growth and weight dispersion under dietary restriction.

These related studies provided foundational knowledge for the

Table 4

Tanks data in the 2 trials used to validate the European seabass (*D. labrax*) model to predict final weight after optimization of hyperparameters. Salinities varied per week in the sequence 15, 38, 21, 33, 27, 45 ppt, except for the control group of trial 1 (Tanks group G4 below). The tank is named W<fish weight>T<temperature>R<replicate>, for control group T is replaced by C.

Tank	number of fish	initial		final observed		final predicted		hyperparameter		
		weight		weight		weight		FCR	dominance	efficiency
		mean	std	mean	std	mean	std			
First trial - Tanks group G1 - Temperature: 17°C										
W23T17R1	24	22.81	3.40	50.53	7.91	52.55	7.20	1.19	3.9 %	70.0 %
W23T17R2	24	22.73	3.57	47.90	7.50	49.27	7.88	1.27	1.0 %	70.0 %
W23T17R3	24	23.21	3.13	46.26	6.37	49.76	6.03	1.41	3.9 %	70.0 %
First trial - Tanks group G2 - Temperature: 21°C										
W23T21R1	24	22.84	3.70	64.34	9.30	64.32	9.75	1.15	3.2 %	83.3 %
W23T21R2	24	22.93	3.13	65.36	9.23	65.56	8.68	1.24	25.2 %	83.7 %
W23T21R3	24	22.68	3.08	66.93	8.33	66.97	8.21	1.21	18.1 %	86.4 %
First trial - Tanks group G3 - Temperature: 26°C										
W23T26R1	24	22.70	3.22	73.47	8.41	73.54	8.62	1.25	6.8 %	105.0 %
W23T26R2	24	22.81	3.43	67.76	13.51	68.57	10.34	1.10	24.2 %	85.0 %
W23T26R3	24	22.63	3.18	74.89	10.85	75.09	10.35	1.08	22.5 %	75.7 %
First trial - Tanks group G4 - Temperature: 21°C (Control group of first trial)										
W22C21R1	24	23.27	3.13	67.79	8.76	67.76	8.95	1.15	28.8 %	84.1 %
W22C21R2	24	22.65	3.73	64.68	11.47	65.16	10.42	1.11	17.4 %	82.3 %
W22C21R3	24	22.81	3.37	69.44	10.07	69.71	10.17	1.13	23.4 %	87.8 %
Second trial - Tanks group G5 - Temperature: 17°C										
W86T17R1	22	86.05	12.64	137.21	20.62	137.83	18.55	1.24	23.1 %	70.0 %
W86T17R2	22	85.79	13.62	136.91	21.82	137.80	20.24	1.25	25.2 %	70.1 %
W86T17R3	22	85.91	15.84	135.24	23.46	137.81	20.87	1.23	28.1 %	70.2 %
Second trial - Tanks group G6 - Temperature: 21°C										
W86T21R1	22	86.10	14.39	150.41	20.57	150.61	19.91	1.23	21.7 %	87.6 %
W86T21R2	22	85.80	15.30	148.87	22.08	149.59	19.77	1.17	22.2 %	84.6 %
W86T21R3	22	85.95	13.94	133.93	19.91	134.05	19.67	1.41	21.4 %	70.5 %
Second trial - Tanks group G7 - Temperature: 26°C										
W86T26R1	22	85.74	16.57	152.69	25.03	153.68	20.33	1.26	28.2 %	88.4 %
W86T26R2	22	85.95	13.95	168.45	29.26	170.22	22.50	1.20	25.4 %	108.8 %
W86T26R3	22	85.77	15.93	174.95	25.98	176.38	23.30	1.07	27.2 %	115.9 %

Fig. 10. Comparison of observed values on all 21 tanks of 2 trials and the corresponding prediction for: final weight mean (left) and standard deviation (right). This chart evaluates the prediction error as the closer to the diagonal line, the better the results.

approach used in modeling European seabass (*D. Labrax*) and were extended to address weight dispersion. However, none of the models presented use machine learning techniques for predicting weight dispersion, and there is almost no data from farmers available for analysis and comparison.

As European seabass (*D. labrax*) is aggressive in the dispute for food, the key point on the weight dispersion is the modeling of the influence of size and dominance by stochastic process at the simulation of the fish

feed dispute at the pellet level. Those processes determine the distribution of the feed between the individuals in the population, then forward digestion processes uses the models for growth and water parameters as already modeled. Almost all models available apply the growth for the average population or even if the simulation is at the individual level, they summarize the parameters as the mean or summed effect.

In the current framework, the dominance index and the body weight

Table 5

Performance metric of European seabass (*D. labrax*) model with hyperparameters optimized to predict trial's tanks final weight.

Metric	Predictor	
	final weight	
	mean	std
R ²	0.999	0.903
MSE	1.60	5.10
RMSE	1.27	2.26
RMSPE	2.1 %	10.4 %
MAE	0.87	1.49
MAPE	1.1 %	8.1 %
SMAPE	1.1 %	8.6 %

Table 6

Results of Breusch-Pagan Lagrange Multiplier test applied to ML regressors predictions and optimized hyperparameters models outputs.

ML Regressor	Metric		homoscedasticity
	p-value		
	Lagrange multiplier	F-statistic	
Final weight CV	2.44e-10	2.36e-10	No
Relative Growth mean	2.86e-85	9.85e-87	No
Final weight mean	0.6462	0.6658	Yes
Final weight std	0.0029	0.0014	No

of the fish decisively determine the availability of food and influence the weight dispersion based on feed amount and the feeding regime. Feeding intervals are crucial, with inadequate feeding increasing weight dispersion due to dominance competition. Conversely, adequate feeding reduces drastically the dominance and size effects and focuses on gut capacity. Incorrect feeding strategies can drastically affect weight dispersion.

Standard deviation as a metric assumes a Gaussian weight distribution, which may no longer apply after grading. Additional parameters or cumulative distribution values at the percentiles may be required for better characterization, complicating prediction models.

Preliminary assessments using existing data from nutritional trials shows the method viability, but further research is needed to accurately predict the weight distribution of European seabass (*D. labrax*) for practical use in aquaculture.

Future work includes refining the components of the simulation model, conducting detailed data collection trials, calibrating the DES simulation, creating comprehensive scenarios, conducting ML model sensitivity analysis, validating species-specific ML models with production data, and ensuring the validation of the hyperparameterization. It also includes tracking individual fish (using computer vision) and measuring biomass on a large scale.

Although the objective of this study is to model the European seabass species, the conceptual design of the method can be applied to other species with similar rearing conditions and the need for gradings during the production cycle. These outcomes can benefit a broader range of aquaculture farmers.

As the model for the European seabass species is developed, its customization for specific tanks will be integrated into the model management software workflow. The model serves two primary functions: First, as a planning tool to predict growth stages, grading, harvesting, and production outcomes in terms of biomass, size classes, and production timing. Second, as part of control systems to monitor conditions and adapt rearing processes, primarily feeding, to achieve planned objectives. Improved planning and execution result in more controlled outcomes and reduced production risks. Given the 18–24 months required for seabass growth, the aquaculture industry faces long lead times, and the current lack of management tools increases the economic risk of this vital food production activity.

6. Conclusion

This research presents a methodology for predicting weight dispersion in aquaculture production units using both Discrete Event Simulation (DES) and Machine Learning (ML) modeling. The approach involves two main steps: first, the development of a generic model with hyperparameters for the species, followed by fine-tuning the model for a specific fish stock and production tank by adjusting the hyperparameters.

The validation of a model for European seabass (*D. labrax*), using existing initial and final weight data from 21 tanks in two laboratory growth trials yielded significant results. The model achieved an R² of 99.9 % and a MAPE of 1.1 % in predicting the average final weight and an R² of 90.3 % with a MAPE of 8.1 % in predicting the standard deviation of the final weight.

These findings reinforce the suitability of this method for predicting weight dispersion. Further improvements can be achieved by refining its implementation with more comprehensive data and complex equations related to ingestion, digestion, and excretion processes. Conducting trials with live fish is crucial for calibrating and validating the DES simulation.

This study successfully demonstrated the ability of ML to replicate daily aggregated simulation results of DES based on input parameters. The model's adaptability for customization to specific tanks and its scalability, achieved through lower time and computational resource requirements, are key features that make the ML model suitable for practical implementation in production systems.

The paper presents the following key contributions and outcomes:

- An **event-based model** for fish feeding behavior was developed, focusing on dominance hierarchy and the spatial distribution of feeding. This model utilizes probability distribution functions and stochastic processing to simulate feeding disputes.
- A Discrete Event System (DES) was created to simulate fish growth processes, feeding dynamics, and water quality assessment. The DES model is driven by events related to the distribution of feeding units and encompasses the ingestion, digestion, and excretion processes of individual fish. The **feasibility** of the DES model in predicting the weight distribution of European seabass is demonstrated.
- A surrogate machine learning (ML) model was developed and trained with simulated data. This surrogate model summarizes daily results, runs much faster, and consumes fewer resources, allowing its use in control systems and management software. The **scalability** of the ML surrogate model enables the application of the simulated knowledge on a production scale.
- A parameterized fish species model was developed, adaptable for specific fish stocks in aquaculture tanks or ponds. This model provides **adaptability** for each production unit and fish stock through a hyperparameter optimization process.
- An **end-to-end method** was introduced to predict the growth of fish stocks throughout production cycles, including the management of multiple tank relocations during grading processes.

Predicting growth and weight dispersion is a key success factor for the planning and management of aquaculture production units, leading to better economic results and a reduced ecological footprint. The methodology proposed in this study is an important step toward achieving this objective.

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CRedit authorship contribution statement

Luiz Claudio Navarro: Writing – original draft, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Ana Azevedo:** Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Anibal Matos:** Supervision. **Anderson Rocha:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Rodrigo Ozorio:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision,

Project administration, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

Appendix. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.aqrep.2024.102315](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aqrep.2024.102315).

Appendix. Visual representation of the steps of the proposed methodology

Step 1 – DES simulation species model implementation

Fig. 11. Methodology step 1 process.

Step 2 – Machine learning species model implementation

Fig. 12. Methodology step 2 process.

Step 3 and 4 – model customization

Fig. 13. Methodology steps 3 and 4 process.

Step 5 – model use in production

Parameters associated with partial fish stock follow the fish transfers initializing new model customization

Fig. 14. Methodology step 5 process.

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